

Study of Respirable Dust in Ambient Air of Bikaner City and Its Impact on Human Health

P.D. Charan and Hemlata Sahel

Department of Environmental Science, Maharaja Ganga Singh University, Bikaner-334004

Abstract: Monthly and seasonal analysis of Respirable Suspended Particulate Matter (RSPM) and Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) was done at industrial, traffic, residential and sensitive locations of Bikaner city. In this study, SPM and RSPM were estimated at 10 representative locations in urban area and one village area for control. The highest level of RSPM ($508.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and SPM ($1156.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was recorded in the month of November and June at Industrial site (Beechwal Industrial Area), respectively. The level of RSPM ($368.45 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at industrial locations and SPM ($987.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at traffic locations (Kot gate) was highest during the winter season. Highest level of SPM ($683.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) was found in summer at industrial location (Karni Industrial Area). The level of pollutants crossed the limits of National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) laid down by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB). These pollutants may pose detrimental effect on human health, as exposures to these are associated with cardiovascular and respiratory diseases with increased risk of mortality and morbidity.

Key words: RSPM • SPM • National Ambient Air Quality Standards

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution poses a worldwide threat to human health and environment. Air pollution in urban area is mainly due to emissions of industrial gases and traffic related particulates, which undergo dispersion, transport and chemical reaction in the atmosphere and are deposited as gaseous ions, solid and liquid particles. In developing countries, the air quality crisis in urban areas is attributed to vehicular emissions, which contributes 40-80% of total air pollution [1]. There are evidences that air quality is worsening in the developing countries.

Pollutants related to health related disorders in urban area include NO_2 , suspended particulate matter, atmospheric aerosols ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}) and ozone (O_3) [2-3]. Like many other cities of India, the ambient air quality of Bikaner is also being deteriorated. During the last decade, Bikaner has witnessed an exponential increase in vehicles, both personal and commercial. Emissions from heavily loaded transport and old vehicles are badly maintained. Automobiles contribute

significantly to the pollution problems. Suspended particulate matter and respirable dusts are regarded as major air pollutant in India [4]. The level of SPM (Suspended Particulate Matter) and RSPM (Respirable Suspended Particulate Matter) in urban environment is of great concern as several studies indicate that particulate matter (coarse and fine particulates) may induce severe effects on public health [5]. The major anthropogenic sources of particulate matter are re-suspension of industrial dust and soil, suspension of soil (farming, mining, unpaved roads), combustion of oil, coal, wood and diesel exhaust particulates. In urban areas, about 50% of the particulate matter is estimated to be from traffic generated emissions [6]. India is rapidly developing country where air pollution levels are steadily rising especially in metro cities and industrial areas. However, report on ambient air quality, especially with reference to the RSPM and SPM in arid region of India are scare. The present investigation has been, therefore, carried out with the objective to assess the level of RSPM and SPM in urban environment of Bikaner city.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was carried out during the period of one year from July, 2011 to June, 2012. The sampling sites were selected on the basis of traffic load, location of industrial area, sensitivity of the location from air pollution point of view etc. Ten sampling sites viz. Beechwal Industrial Area, Kot gate, Karni industrial area, PBM hospital, JNV colony, Panchsati circle, Railway station, Rani Bazar industrial area, Ganganagar road and Poogal fanta, while MGS university campus was selected as control due to its location outside area near Nal village. Suspended particulate matter and Respirable suspended particulate matter were analyzed by using High Volume Sampler and Respirable Dust Sampler (Instrumex IPM 115 BL/NL) using GF/A, Whatmann (8"x10") filter paper [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study was focused on the assessment of Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) and Respirable Suspended Particulate Matter (RSPM) concentration at various areas of Bikaner city of western Rajasthan. Monthly and seasonal analysis of SPM and RSPM was done at industrial, traffic, residential and sensitive locations of the city. The sampling was done twice a month at the various selected locations during the study period. The highest annual average concentration of SPM was observed at Beechwal industrial area ($683.80\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) followed by Kot gate ($671\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Rani Bazar industrial

area ($574\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). The data on SPM concentration reveals that the value of SPM (<10 micron size) level is much higher than the maximum permissible limits ($60\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) prescribed by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards [8]. However, it was noted that at control site (MGS University campus located near Nal village) the level of annual average concentration of SPM was found to be well under the maximum permissible limits (Fig. 1). Results of the present study fairly support the earlier findings [9-11]. Similarly, the highest annual average concentration of RSPM was observed at Beechwal industrial area ($357.17\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) followed by Rani Bazar industrial area ($318.31\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Karni Industrial area ($284.41\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). While, it was observed that the lowest annual concentration RSPM was found at MGS University campus ($32.61\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (control site), followed by Panchsati circle ($36.35\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and JNV Colony ($41.65\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), respectively (Fig. 2). The results of the study are in line of the studies carried out in the past [12, 13]. The results of the present study revealed that the SPM and RSPM concentration at different selected locations are much higher than the maximum permissible limits prescribed by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). However, the SPM and RSPM load in the ambient air of the control site (MGS university campus) was found well under the maximum permissible limits. The excessive amount of the SPM and RSPM may be correlated with the poor traffic management, narrow roads in the interior part of the old city, over crowding of cattle in urban area, illegal parking of vehicles etc.

Fig. 1: Comparative assessment of SPM concentration at various sites in Bikaner

Fig. 2: Comparative assessment of RSPM concentration at various sites in Bikaner

The higher concentration of SPM and RSPM near the Kot gate site may be correlated with the railway crossing at the main road. It was observed that the main road from Kot gate connects the old city from the major locations of the new settlements and other major markets of the city and hence, the busy railway track in the area leads to congestion of road traffic for many times throughout the day and night, which accelerate the air pollution problem in the area.

Since the city is located in the core area of the Thar desert, the dust related health hazards are very common in the residents residing here. The problem became more severe due to industrial exhaust, vehicular pollution and other anthropogenic activities. It was found that harmful emission into the air is a symbol for environmental force that seriously affects human health, natural life and agriculture; thus leading to major loss on the nation's economy [14]. Therefore, strict traffic management, proper planning for controlling illegal parking, proper maintenance of vehicles, proper implementation of Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981 are the need of the time to mitigate the air pollution in the urban area of Bikaner.

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